

SHARING OF SUCCESS STORIES: POLITENESS STRATEGIES OF COMMENCEMENT SPEAKERS

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Sharing of Success Stories: Politeness Strategies of Commencement Speakers

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Abstract

In context of ceremonial discourse, commencement speeches serve as a significant platform for sharing success narratives, imparting words of wisdom and giving motivation as well as inspiration to graduating individuals. This study undertook a discourse analysis to unveil and explore the employment of politeness strategies by commencement speakers in sharing success stories during graduation ceremonies. Limited to twenty (20) YouTube videos, the research scrutinized the linguistic choices within the speeches. Among the identified strategies, positive politeness emerged as the most frequently employed, followed by the bald on-record approach, while the utilization of negative politeness was less common. Notably, the off-record strategy was absent from the speeches. The examination of these strategies' sheds light on the nuanced linguistic techniques employed by commencement speakers to engage their audiences and convey success narratives. This study contributes to our understanding of discourse in ceremonial contexts, highlighting the importance of linguistic choices in conveying messages of achievement and inspiration

Keywords: *discourse analysis, politeness strategies, commencement speakers, commencement speeches, graduation ceremonies*

Introduction

Graduations or commencement exercises mark the beginning of a new phase in the life of individuals. With this, inspiration becomes necessary as they journey on a new path. Graduation speeches, with their huge stage and attentive audience, serve a purpose far beyond formality. They are the result of years of hard effort, development, and shared experiences. These speeches provide an excellent opportunity to reflect on the class's collective journey, recognize accomplishments, and inspire the graduating class as they embark on the uncharted experience of the future. More often than not, a commencement speech becomes an essential part of such ceremonies because it serves as an avenue for a speaker to inspire and motivate students on the journey they are about to face. Thus, the quality of the message that a commencement speaker shares to the audience is very important as this defines the impact that it leaves on the audience (Daniel, 2023).

In the international setting, particularly in Baltimore, United States, concerns were raised about the choice of commencement speaker during the winter commencement exercises at the University of Maryland. The selected speaker was a renowned politician and alumna of the university. However, there was criticism regarding the speaker's moral stance, deemed incongruent with the values that should be imparted to a room full of graduates. The argument emphasized that the selection of speakers should not be solely based on fame and financial success; rather, the crucial criteria should be the wisdom they share with the graduates and their families (Keene, 2019).

In the national setting, specifically in Camarines Sur, an issue about a plagiarized graduation speech from Mr. Jayvee Ayen, the batch valedictorian of Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges (CSPC) batch 2022 swarmed the news as audiences observed the similarities of his speech to another commencement speech given by a student from Far Eastern University (FEU) from the year 2019 (Sto. Tomas, 2022). He specifically used the same opening lines saying “. Lang, the short term for the Filipino word 'lamang', which means 'just' or 'only,'" which was identical with the FEU student's introductory sentence in her earlier speech, and throughout the speech, the theme continued to sound alike (Ranara, 2022).

With such in mind, this study holds significant social relevance because commencement speeches have a tremendous impact on graduates' perspectives, influencing their thinking as they begin on new endeavors. The language used and politeness approaches employed in these speeches reflect cultural norms, providing unique insights into varied social perspectives about success and challenges. This understanding is critical for establishing cultural competence and effective communication across diverse cultures. In relation to this, such a study is sufficiently urgent since commencement speakers have a significant impact on the aspirations and perspectives of graduating students. Decoding politeness strategies is essential for facilitating pleasant relationships in our rapidly globalizing society, where cultural diversity is increasingly interconnected. Furthermore, because commencement speakers typically represent notable individuals, their communication style has the potential to impact broader cultural discourse. Immediate research into these approaches is essential to broaden our understanding of cultural dynamics, improve inclusive communication, and support leaders seeking to express messages of success and motivation that resonate across diverse social contexts.

At present, there are existing studies about utilizing politeness strategies in various discourse contexts. Like the study of Kuzhevskaya (2018) entitled, “Politeness Strategies in Business English Discourse”, study of “Monsefi and Hadidi (2015) Male and Female EFL Teachers' Politeness Strategies in Oral Discourse and their Effects on the Learning Process and Teacher-Student Interaction”, and study of Senowarsito (2020) “Politeness Strategies in Teacher Student Interaction in an EFL Classroom Context” which these related study solely focused on interpersonal communication, business discourse, and language learning contexts, leaving a distinct lack of investigation into the politeness strategies employed by commencement speakers. Unlike prior research, this study focuses at the

politeness strategies used by influential commencement speakers, providing new insights into leadership communication within the context of success-oriented narratives and inspiration. The study's originality comes in its focus on the connection of politeness, leadership, and motivation, offering a holistic knowledge of how language choices affect graduates' perspectives and thinking at this momentous point in time. This study not only fills a gap in the literature, but also contributes to the larger discussion of politeness in many communicative circumstances.

Hence, this study, the researcher carefully followed ethical principles while using known techniques for gathering and analyzing information, ensuring that all possible beneficiaries could understand the findings. The collected data was rigorously evaluated to produce relevant conclusions that were consistent with the study's aims. Subsequently, various dissemination strategies were implemented. Printed copies were made available in the school library for easy access by interested individuals. Furthermore, efforts were made to present the findings at conferences and, where possible, to publish it in respectable journals or on reputable websites. These distribution initiatives seek to increase the accessibility of the important ideas expressed in success stories by commencement speakers, thereby providing essential insights to a larger audience, particularly regarding the use of politeness methods in their addresses.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the goals and purpose of this research, this research aims to give answers to the following research questions:

1. What politeness strategies are used by commencement speakers in their speeches?
2. How do these politeness strategies contribute to the overall message of the commencement speakers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research design in discourse analysis approach, which aims to emphasize the ideologies of politeness and impoliteness by focusing on how commencement speakers interacted with their audience in terms of politeness in combination with the linguistic information provided in the transcript of the text. With these, qualitative researchers sought insights by looking into the nuances of how people articulated their opinions as well as the content of their utterances. Moreover, qualitative research collected and analyzed non-numerical data with the goal of interpreting meaning. It is a qualitative research since it will use a variety of analytic approaches to gather and authenticate social phenomena in a systematic and descriptive manner (Turner, 2020).

In context, a qualitative research design was utilized in this study to analyze the nuanced interplay between politeness and impoliteness ideologies in commencement speeches. The goal is to understand how commencement speakers interacted with their audiences in terms of politeness, utilizing linguistic data taken from the speeches' transcripts. This qualitative method tries to reveal not only the content of opinions but also the manner in which they are communicated by digging into the complexities of expression and communication patterns. The research uses various analytic strategies to authentically capture and interpret the social phenomena inherent in commencement speeches, providing a comprehensive exploration of the complexities surrounding politeness in this specific communicative context.

Moreover, this study employed discourse analysis approach. Discourse analysis, or DA, is an approach of investigating how individuals used language in various contexts. It went beyond just looking at the words themselves to understanding how language was used to express meaning in social and cultural contexts. In fact, discourse analysis was a research approach that examined written or spoken language within its social context and its goal is to understand how language worked in everyday contexts, providing insights into the complexities of communication and its role in determining social dynamics (Limpaecher & Ho, 2023).

In context, discourse analysis was utilized to clarify the nuances of communication within the setting of commencement addresses, notably the ideologies of politeness and impoliteness. This methodology was chosen to go beyond the content of thoughts and give clarity to the nuances of expression and communication patterns. Discourse analysis provided for a nuanced investigation of how commencement presenters connected with their audience in terms of etiquette by scrutinizing linguistic features and language use. It provided a framework for genuinely capturing and interpreting the social phenomena buried in the speeches, allowing for a thorough comprehension of the communicative complexities underlying politeness in this unique environment.

Instrument

The research materials for this study were the commencement speech transcripts for linguistic analysis. It is to analyze how commencement speaker's express politeness when delivering their speeches. The goal was to understand how success stories are shared in a respectful manner within the specific social and cultural framework of commencement addresses.

As such, this study utilized twenty (20) commencement speech videos, gathered by downloading content from an online platform, with a particular emphasis on sourcing from YouTube. Evidently, Braun and Clarke (2013) offer some recommendations regarding the number of research materials to be used. As previously recommended, this study requires a minimum sample size of at least 10-100 research materials as sources to adequately complete the objective of the research and reach data saturation. Hence, a total of 20

commencement speech videos will be considered adequate for the scope of this study.

Furthermore, to ensure a comprehensive examination, the duration of each video had a minimum of fifteen (15) minutes and maximum length of thirty (30) minutes. The selection of commencement speeches aimed to focus on invited speakers renowned for delivering inspirational and motivational content. This approach aims to capture a distinct genre of speeches that often offered wisdom, encouragement, and guidance to graduates as they entered new stages of their life. The study's precise criteria aimed to provide a fair and representative dataset, allowing for a nuanced analysis of both the content and delivery approaches used by the selected commencement speakers.

The researcher selected and used the research corpora with the following set of criteria: (a) commencement speech videos sourced exclusively from reputable online platforms, particularly YouTube, (b) commencement speech videos featuring speakers invited to address graduating audiences with a focus on providing guidance and motivation, (c) commencement speech videos ranging from minimum of fifteen (15) minutes and maximum length of thirty (30) minutes, ensuring a substantial and meaningful analysis, (d) commencement speeches conducted on both national and international setting, particularly within the college level and (e) commencement speech videos spanning from 2020 to the present. Furthermore, the videos that served as the research materials were named CS which stands for Commencement Speech. Thus, the research materials were labeled as CS-01, CS-02, CS-03... CS-20.

Procedure

As a researcher, I went through a variety of processes to collect data and other essential material for the study. Before initiating the study, I communicated with my adviser to determine how to begin the research study and identified the steps required to complete this research.

The data collected for this study focused on the politeness strategies employed by commencement speakers. Specifically, I obtained twenty (20) commencement speeches directly from the YouTube website. These documents played a crucial role in providing a clear understanding for the discourse analysis of politeness in commencement speeches. The collected data underwent thorough treatment and interpretation, and the subsequent chapters presented relevant information to offer a comprehensive view of the research.

The information was analyzed, explored, and treated based on the problems of the study. To concretize ideas, the results were also supported with reflected studies and literature.

Data Analysis

This study specifically set forth to examine how politeness was being used by the speaker in delivering their commencement speech. By using Discourse Analysis (DA) as a research approach, I, as the researcher hoped to generate new knowledge with regards to the extensive researches on the politeness theory in general.

Scholars have recommended that researchers investigating online discussions should utilize frameworks that are built on prior research. As such, in this study, the researcher builds upon Brown and Levinson's (1987) work. The politeness theory was utilized in the analysis to specifically shed light and answers to the research questions which are as follows: (1) politeness strategies are used by commencement speakers in their speeches; and (2) the contribution of politeness strategies to the overall message of the commencement speakers.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in research are a collection of core principles that guide the design and execution of research projects. When engaging with individuals for data collecting, scientists and researchers must continuously adhere to a prescribed code of ethics. Human studies endeavor usually seek to grasp real-world events, investigate treatment efficacy, investigate behaviors, and contribute to various elements of human well-being. As a result, the selection of research topics and the manner in which research is carried out inevitably involve significant ethical considerations (Bhandari, 2022)

Respect for Persons entails that human dignity is a fundamental ethical principle that emphasizes protecting the autonomy of research participants while fully disclosing all aspects of the study, including any potential risks and benefits. Researchers must respect the right of individuals to make their own informed decisions about whether or not to participate in research. Individuals must be given complete information about a study and must be free to choose whether or not to participate in order to be considered autonomous (AVAC, 2023).

Since the current study did not have participants, the researcher still achieved the first principle by ensuring that the authors of the data used in his study were properly cited. The researcher also ensured that any personal information or identifying details were removed or anonymized in the transcription and analysis of the data. Additionally, he also made sure that their analysis and interpretation of the data were accurate and representative of the source material.

Beneficence essentially entails prioritizing the interests and welfare of research participants. This principle emphasizes researchers' efforts to minimize any potential risks to participants while maximizing both personal and societal benefits. When developing a research plan, for example, the beneficence principle encourages us to consider alternative approaches to knowledge acquisition that expose

participants to fewer potential risks (Barrow et al., 2022).

In this context, beneficence prioritizes the well-being and interests of the commencement speakers, who are research participants. It entails ensuring that any possible hazards to them are minimized while maximizing the personal and societal advantages received from the research. In designing the study strategy, the researcher is guided by the beneficence principle to explore alternative techniques that expose the speakers to fewer risks. This ensures a comprehensive and ethical research process that prioritizes the welfare of all individuals involved.

Consent is a document that must be written in simple, understandable language with the goal of minimizing the possibility of coercion or undue influence. It is critical to give people enough time to consider their participation decision before committing. It is critical to emphasize that informed consent entails much more than simply signing a document; it entails a thorough procedure in which participants gain a thorough understanding of the research as well as any potential risks. In order for them to approve, written consent was provided. They agreed to participate in the focus groups and in-depth interviews after receiving approval. Of course, they were informed of the study's findings and recommendations (Siegle, 2023).

The ongoing study does not require written consent from individual participants as it utilizes the analysis of pre-existing language data and does not involve human subjects. Furthermore, all corpora used in the study are obtained from online public domains where the linguistic data is easily accessible to the public. As a result, obtaining permission from individual participants is unnecessary because the data is already publicly available. However, the researcher follows ethical guidelines regarding consent and ensures that the corpus data utilized in the study is gathered and handled in a responsible and ethical manner.

Confidentiality, in the context of human research, also refers to the investigator's agreement with participants through informed consent from participants about how their personally identifiable information will be treated, managed, and shared. People will be willing to share information for research purposes only if it is understood that it will be protected from disclosure outside of the research setting or to unauthorized parties. During the interview, the researcher will emphasize that the participants' identities will be kept private as the study progresses. The researcher will also ensure that only the study's researcher and the relevant field's professor have access to the data (Research Integrity, 2021).

In this study, confidentiality is also guaranteed, even though the thesis does not involve human participants. The researcher takes precautions to maintain the privacy and confidentiality of the individuals whose language is being analyzed in the corpus data. One method is anonymization, which involves eliminating any identifying information that might reveal the identity of the language users. The researcher additionally seeks permission to use the corpus data and follows any applicable copyright or usage limitations to guarantee that the data is utilized ethically and responsibly. In addition, the researcher takes precautions to prevent unauthorized access or distribution of the corpus data by securely keeping it and only sharing it with authorized individuals. The researcher ensures that the privacy and anonymity of the language users in the corpus data are respected by adhering to these ethical criteria, even if the data does not involve human participants.

Justice is ensured as researchers should consider what is fair in terms of participant selection and trial site selection. Concerns have been raised about who bears the risks associated with research and who benefits from it. It establishes a framework for approaching these decisions in a just and equitable manner. People should not be included in studies simply because they belong to a vulnerable group or because they are easier to reach and are less likely to decline participation (Gelling, 2018).

In this study, even though no human subjects are used, the researcher guarantees fairness and equity by obtaining permission to use the corpus data and adhering to any relevant copyright or usage limitations. Additionally, the researcher ensures that the corpus data is anonymized and confidential, especially if it contains sensitive or personal information. Finally, the researcher reports any limitations or potential biases in the study and provides a balanced and nuanced interpretation of the findings to ensure fairness and equity. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher guarantees that the study is carried out in an ethical and responsible manner, even if no human subjects are engaged.

Results and Discussion

This section of the paper presents the results, particularly the politeness strategies such as positive politeness, negative politeness, bald on record, and off-record strategies of the discourse analysis done on commencement speeches. In turn of the data gathering conducted, the following parts of this paper shows how politeness strategies were in play when it comes to the delivery of commencement speeches by the speakers.

Politeness Strategies used by Commencement Speakers in Commencement Speeches

Commencement speeches are deemed to be inspiring and motivational for its audience, which most of the time are students. One of the contributing factors for a speech to be inspiring is its ability to communicate its message well to its audience, and this could be achieved with the use of politeness strategies. Politeness is defined as a way of behaving that puts in consideration the feelings of another person, and is regarded as socially appropriate. In pragmatics, it is said to be the most appropriate way to deliver a message in a given context. Moreover, a study on American and Arabic motivational speeches reveals that positive politeness strategies are used in their delivery

and proves how effective these strategies are in delivering a speech for the audience to appreciate whatever is communicated to them (Bajiri et al., 2022).

This paper analyzes the commencement speeches following Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987). To determine the politeness strategies used in the speeches, the transcript of all commencement speeches was manually read to detect words that depict politeness strategies. These cues were then grouped according to their type, such as positive politeness, negative politeness, bald on-record, or off record, then analyzed accordingly depending on the factors that affected the use of such strategies. The table below presents the analysis of the commencement speeches.

Table 1. Politeness Strategies Utilized in Commencement Speeches

<i>Politeness Strategies</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Positive Politeness	<p>"Hello, good morning!" - CS-04</p> <p>"That's how much I love you, guys" - CS-06</p> <p>"It is truly an honor to be here with you" - CS-03</p> <p>"To all of you graduates please know that from here on out, we are family" - CS-02</p> <p>"You are allowed to want things" - CS-03</p> <p>"Congratulations!" - CS-05</p> <p>"Thank you very much" - CS-19</p> <p>"Wow!" - CS-18</p> <p>"I feel your pain" - CS-05</p> <p>"So, you can trust me" - CS-04</p> <p>"Godspeed" - CS-07</p> <p>"We are all very proud of you, UP" - CS-10</p> <p>"Graduation is a big achievement under any circumstances." - CS-15</p> <p>"... and God bless you as you enter this new exciting and promising chapter of your lives." - CS-11</p> <p>"... in fact, you're supposed to be the good news right ... the good news I have for you today LMU is that there are worlds out there waiting to be forever changed by you Loyola Marymount University Graduating class of 2022." - CS-20</p> <p>"You got through a year of quarantines, zoom classes, masks, nasal swabs, and I'm guessing more take-out food than you thought you'd eat in a lifetime—and you're graduating." - CS-13</p>
Negative Politeness	<p>"...and I know it can be really overwhelming figuring out who to be and when, who you are now and how to act in order to get where you wanna go" - CS-01</p> <p>"You might feel smart and satisfied with your experience here, but unprepared. Or you may feel lost for a bit as you figure out what moves to make, or where to go, and how to make the most of the time and hella money you spent here." - CS-04</p> <p>"I hate to break it to you but the real wisdom that comes with age is that you gain a greater appreciation for just how much you don't know" - CS-08</p> <p>"It breaks my heart to have to tell you that you can be talented, you can be gifted, you can be on the dean's list, you can be a scholar of the first order, you can be an outstanding engineer, you're going to be a great teacher, you can be a doctor, a lawyer, an engineer but I will tell you that if you're black or brown you will go places where you're going to have to navigate a presumption of dangerousness and guilt." - CS-12</p> <p>Going to be a great teacher, you can be a doctor, a lawyer, an engineer but I will tell you that if you're black or brown you will go places where you're going to have to navigate a presumption of dangerousness and guilt." - CS-12</p> <p>"... and I don't care how hard Life After College gets and it's gonna get hard." - CS-14</p> <p>"Maybe you got an email or two about it" - CS-17</p>
Bald On-record	<p>"I beseech you to remember the lessons of the office." - CS-09</p> <p>"I am asking you today to use them on behalf of our democracy." - CS-05</p> <p>"I challenge you, the graduating class of 2022, to find your toughness." - CS-06</p> <p>"Decide what is yours to hold and let the rest go." - CS-01</p> <p>"Build and tap into your community." - CS-04</p> <p>"Trust and believe that your Stanford family will show up for you in unexpected ways." - CS-04</p> <p>"... at every table you find yourself, get aligned and stay aligned." - CS-20</p>

Positive Politeness

Positive politeness strategies are utilized to lessen the threat brought by the speaker to the positive face of the audience. The use of this strategy aims to elevate the listeners' positive feeling about themselves in ways like giving compliments, appreciating, considering their needs and wants, and by promoting inclusion and oneness. In this analysis, the following positive politeness strategies were analyzed from the commencement speeches.

As presented in Table 1, the positive politeness strategy labeled as CS-04 is used as a greeting. Two greetings, specifically “hello” and “good morning” were uttered in the beginning of the speech keep and maintain social relationships. The speaker used this greeting to maintain a positive connection with the audience at the start of the speech. It is used to enhance the hearer’s positive face. The statement below showcases how this positive politeness strategy is utilized in the speech.

“Hello, good morning!” (CS-04)

Similarly, the use of a politeness strategy as a greeting was also detected in another speech labeled as CS-05. This specifically uses “good morning” and addresses the students through the use of their university’s name, “Duke”. It was used similarly, as a way of opening a speech to establish rapport and create a connection with the audience and uplift the listener’s positive face. The statement below presents how the positive politeness strategy was used in the speech.

“Good morning, Duke” (CS-05)

Moreover, positive politeness was also detected as evidenced by the use of in-group identity markers or the use of common names to address the listeners. This method involves the utterance of endearments such as “love,” “bro,” “sis,” and others. As seen on the statement labeled as CS-0-06, the identity marker used was “guys”, which ensure that there is no threat to the hearer’s face. This politeness strategy was uttered as stated below.

“That’s how much I love you, guys” (CS-06)

Comparably, the same identity marker was used in another commencement speech shown in the statement labeled as CS1. The use of the “guys” as a call name signals the audience to be part of the speaker’s social group which promote inclusion and reducing social distance. It was utilized as a positive politeness strategy as stated below.

“What you guys all experienced at some point in the last four years, right?” (CS-01)

Another positive politeness strategy analyzed from the commencement speeches was the expression of the speaker’s interest to the hearer. The speaker expresses his/her interest in sharing the event with them and is telling them how it is a privilege to be speaking to them. CS-03 enhances the positive face of the listener since the speaker is taking the opportunity to be with them something special. I hope you know how proud I am to share this day with you.

“It is truly an honor to be here with you” (CS-03)

Likewise, another speaker also used the same style by expressing how much he appreciates the achievement of the graduates, stating that it was a proud moment for the speaker. This positive politeness strategy is presented in CS-01.

“I hope you know how proud I am to share this day with you” (CS-01)

Another positive politeness strategy incorporated in the commencement speeches is the use of words that promote oneness between the speaker and the audience. In the statement the use of the words “we” and “family” were used in CS-02. These words convey a message of support towards the listener, thus enhancing their positive face. This positive politeness strategy was incorporated as stated below.

“To all of you graduates please know that from here on out, we are family” (CS-02)

In the same manner, CS-01 also expresses a sense of inclusion. This is seen in the use of the word us” which foster inclusion and shared identity. The speaker recognizes the achievement of the audience by sharing an insight that all of them had to do it with someone.

“Not a single one of us here today has done it alone.” (CS-01)

Additionally, the promotion of a hearer’s autonomy is also one method of using a positive politeness strategy. In an analyzed speech, the statement below shows how the speaker recognizes the hearer’s autonomy by validating their desire of their wants. The positive politeness strategy is utilized in the speech as presented below.

“You are allowed to want things.” (CS-03)

Also, the use of congratulatory words as a positive politeness strategy was analyzed in the given commencement speeches. All analyzed speeches used the word “congratulations” to appreciate or feeling to be pleased with success and the achievement of the students as they finished their college education. This is an example of a strategy that boosts the positive face of the hearer. This strategy was used in the speech as presented below.

“Congratulations!” (CS-05)

Furthermore, a positive politeness strategy was also detected through the speaker’s expression of thanks. In most speeches, “thank you” was used to recognize and appreciate the efforts and welcome of the audience. This positive politeness strategy was utilized in the speech as presented below.

“Thank you very much” (CS-19)

Another use of positive politeness strategy in the speeches was the incorporation of exaggeration. In the statement CS-18, the word “wow” was uttered as a reaction to the positive attitude of the audience towards the speakers. Thus, this reaction from the speaker also enhanced the positive feeling of the hearer as their response was also appreciated. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“Wow” (CS-18)

Similarly, CS-08 also uttered the same word as an expression of amusement towards the reaction of the audience. This expression is also shown below.

“Wow” (CS-08)

One more use of positive politeness strategy in the speeches was sharing the same feelings with the audience. In this specific example below, the speaker sympathized with the hearer’s painful feeling. Therefore, the hearer felt supported and had an enhanced positive face. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“I feel your pain” (CS-05)

Another use of positive politeness strategy in the speeches was the expression of assurance or reassurance to the hearer’s thoughts, feelings, and emotions. The use of the word “so” below gives assurance to the hearer that he/she can trust the speaker with whatever she advises. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“So, you can trust me” (CS-04)

Likewise, assurance was also analyzed in the statement below the speaker is assuring the listener that if ever he/she still has an ill feeling, it is okay and is valid. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“... and if you don't feel it yet well, that's okay, too” (CS-05)

To top it off, the use of well wishes as a positive politeness strategy in the speeches was also identified. This statement expresses the speaker's intention of wishing the hearer a successful journey from the moment of their graduation. This statement enhances the positive face of the hearer and avoids any threat to it.

“Godspeed” (CS-07)

Similarly, the same style was used to wish the audience a good life from then on. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“May goodness and mercy follow you all the days of your lives” (CS-07)

Another utterance, CS-10, also expresses a positive politeness strategy. This uses an utterance that recognizes the achievement of the students by saying “proud of you”. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“We are all very proud of you, UP” (CS-10)

Moreover, another expression of positive politeness is through recognizing the achievements of the hearer. Since the setting is in a graduation event, the speaker emphasizes how this milestone is one great achievement for the students. This is different from other congratulatory statements since it is uttered in a way that it directly states the achievement and does not only congratulate. The use of this positive politeness strategy in the speech is presented below.

“Graduation is a big achievement under any circumstances.” (CS-15)

Furthermore, another positive politeness strategy detected is the utterance of the speaker stating an awareness of the audiences’ positive future. Through the statement below, the speaker wishes the students well in their new journey after graduating.

“... and God bless you as you enter this new exciting and promising chapter of your lives.” (CS-11)

Another use of positive politeness strategy in the speeches was the expression of giving compliments or by praising the graduates. In this statement, the phrase “good news” emphasizes that the audience or the graduates have potential to influence positive change in the world. Through recognizing and encouraging their potential impact, it fosters a supportive and motivation among the graduate, enhancing their positive self-perception.

“... in fact, you're supposed to be the good news right ... the good news I have for you today LMU is that there are worlds out there waiting to be forever changed by you Loyola Marymount University Graduating class of 2022” (CS-20)

The last positive politeness strategy analyzed from the speeches is the use of humor. There are different types of humor applied, making sure that the punt or joke remains relatable to the audience. However, it is made sure that the jokes uttered do not offend any of the

hearer as it may defeat its nature of being a positive politeness strategy. In the statement below, the speaker jokes about how many take-outs they have made throughout the course of their school year amidst the pandemic. The statement below presents how humor was utilized as a positive politeness strategy in the speech.

“You got through a year of quarantines, zoom classes, masks, nasal swabs, and I’m guessing more take-out food than you thought you’d eat in a lifetime—and you’re graduating.” (CS-13)

Negative Politeness

Negative politeness strategies have the goal to lessen the impact on the hearer’s negative face. These levels out the tendency of the speaker to interfere with the hearer’s self-autonomy. With the use of politeness cues, the impact on the hearer’s negative face is minimized. The following are the negative politeness strategies analyzed from the commencement speeches as presented below.

In Table 1 the first negative politeness strategy identified was the use of sympathy towards the negative face of the hearer. Specifically, the statement agrees with the overwhelming feeling that the audience might have in facing the challenge of finding themselves, yet the imposition was lessened. Thus, this statement puts a threat to the hearer’s negative face and is considered to be a negative politeness strategy. The use of this strategy in the speech is as presented below.

“... and I know it can be really overwhelming figuring out who to be and when, who you are now and how to act in order to get where you wanna go” (CS-01)

Another negative politeness strategy analyzed was the use of hedging. In the statement the imposition was lessened through the use of the word “might” as this was a sign that the hearer is open to the possibility that his/her statement might be wrong. However, the speaker still mentions words that negatively impact the hearer’s face such as being unprepared and being uncertain. Thus, this is an example of a negative politeness strategy and it poses a threat to the negative face of the hearer. This negative politeness strategy was utilized in the speech as presented below.

“You might feel smart and satisfied with your experience here, but unprepared. Or you may feel lost for a bit as you figure out what moves to make, or where to go, and how to make the most of the time and hella money you spent here.” (CS-04)

The next negative politeness strategy identified in the speeches is the method of smoothing out and lessening the amount of infliction towards the hearer. With the utterance of “I hate to break it to you” it reflects that the speaker is somehow hesitant on stating his words. Still, this threatens the negative face of the hearer and is analyzed as a negative politeness strategy. This negative politeness strategy was utilized in the speech as presented below.

“I hate to break it to you but the real wisdom that comes with age is that you gain a greater appreciation for just how much you don't know.” (CS-09)

Also, the use of the words “it breaks my heart” to lessen the impact of the threat to the negative face of the hearer was detected from the speeches. The speaker wanted to express how the real world could be unfair especially when it comes to opportunities for people of color. A negative politeness strategy was utilized in this utterance as presented below.

“It breaks my heart to have to tell you that you can be talented, you can be gifted, you can be on the dean's list, you can be a scholar of the first order, you can be an outstanding engineer, you're going to be a great teacher, you can be a doctor, a lawyer, an engineer but I will tell you that if you're black or brown you will go places where you're going to have to navigate a presumption of dangerousness and guilt.” (CS-12)

Additionally, an expression of a statement that emphasizes a p=negative thing that may be experienced by the audience is utilized as another negative politeness strategy. In the statement, the speaker emphasized how much of a struggle life could be. The use of this statement is presented below, labeled CS-14.

“... and I don't care how hard Life After College gets and it's gonna get hard.” (CS-14)

Lately, the use of the word “maybe” also depicts a negative politeness strategy. In the speech, this word was used to tell if the audience was able to receive an email. Since “maybe” was used, it emphasized doubtfulness in the actions of the speaker. The utilization of this strategy is presented in the statement CS-17.

“Maybe you got an email or two about it” (CS-17)

Bald On-record

Bald on-record strategies are used to interfere with the hearer’s face by uttering words that clearly and directly state a course of action. Most of the time, this strategy does not care to lessen the threat imposed on the hearer’s face. It is used to give commands that need an urgent reaction, an efficient response, and a sense of alertness. In this analysis, the bald on-record strategies observed are presented below.

In the table above, the first style of bald on-record strategy implies a sense of urgency. The statement below uses the word “beseech”

which means asking fervently or with urgency. The statement is telling the audience to remember whatever was thought to them by the office. S3 is an example of this statement as presented below.

“I beseech you to remember the lessons of the office.” (CS-09)

Similarly, urgency can be identified in another bald on-record strategy detected from the speech. In this statement, the word “now” was used to show that the audience should lend their ears to whatever the speaker is about to say as this is very important. This bald on-record strategy was utilized in the speech as presented below.

“Now listen.” (CS-07)

Another observation of a bald on-record strategy from the speeches is the utterance of a request. This request demands action from the listener. Specifically, the statement below asks the audience to use whatever skill was imparted to them in whatever way that will benefit them as they have the freedom to do so. The statement below presents how this strategy was utilized in the speech.

“I am asking you today to use them on behalf of our democracy.” (CS-05)

Additionally, the act of challenging the audience through the use of words as a bald on-record strategy was also analyzed in the speeches. The statement “I challenge you” implies an action to be done by the audience. The speaker does not care about whatever the impact is on the hearer’s face and instead he/she pushes the hearer to act so. The statement below shows how this bald on-record strategy is used in the speech.

“I challenge you, the graduating class of 2022, to find your toughness.” (CS-06)

Moreover, the promotion of an efficient course of action is an example of a bald on-record strategy. In the given example, CS-01 implies that the audience must decide on which experiences and ownerships to keep so that they can let go of whatever is not necessary to move forward. This tells the listener what to do so as not to waste time and effort. The statement below shows how this strategy was utilized in the speech.

“Decide what is yours to hold and let the rest go.” (CS-01)

In the same manner, the next statement also shares an efficient course of action. This tells the audience to take over so that they can make a change in this world without wasting any more opportunities. The statement below shows how this strategy was utilized in the speech.

“Wanting is not enough. To change things, you have to take over.” (CS-03)

Furthermore, the use of any task-oriented imposition on the listener may be an example of a bald on-record strategy. In this example the speaker is asking the audience to start collaborating with the people in their community and do some action. The utilization of this bald on-record strategy is presented below.

“Build and tap into your community.” (CS-04)

Likewise, the following statement also demands an action of enhancing whatever knowledge has been acquired by the audience to make it useful. The statement below shows how this strategy was utilized in the speech.

“Cultivate what you learned.” (CS-06)

The expression of care towards the hearer may also be an example of a bald on-record strategy. The statement asks the audience to believe that there is a community that has their back. This statement promotes care and support to the audience; however, it still imposes the audience to believe the listener. Thus, it is an example of a bald on-record strategy as presented below.

“Trust and believe that your Stanford family will show up for you in unexpected ways.” (CS-04)

To top it off, an application of a bald-on record strategy was utilized through a direct statement of the speaker to tell the audience what to do every time they are faced with something. The statement below shows how the speaker demands the audience to get aligned and stay aligned every time.

“... at every table you find yourself, get aligned and stay aligned.” (CS-20)

Overall, the politeness strategy with the most examples detected from the speeches was the positive politeness strategy. Positive politeness strategy improves the speech’s overall message since it comes off as more friendly to the audience due to the fact that it aligns with their positive face. It involves words that support the feelings and perceptions of the audience, making it easier for the audience to accept and agree on what the speaker says. Also, other politeness strategies such as negative politeness, and bald on-record strategies are still detected because all of these contribute to the effectiveness of the message delivered. However, no bald off record strategy or the utterance of an indirect message to do a certain action was identified from the discourse analysis done on the given commencement speeches.

Communication Accommodation and Its Impact to the Overall Message of the Commencement Speaker

To answer the second research question “How do these politeness strategies contribute to the overall message of the commencement speakers?” an analysis of the communication accommodation style present on the commencement speeches was done. Consequently, this theory was utilized to help speaker adjust their communication styles to either converge with or diverge from their audience’s style these involves aligning speech patterns, tone, and content to create rapport and foster a sense of unity.

Upon analysis of the different commencement speeches studied in this paper, all of the speeches incorporated a convergence accommodation in their speeches. The convergence accommodation is similar with the use of positive politeness strategies wherein cues are uttered to cut down the barrier between the audience and the speaker, which makes a connection and rapport. All the collected commencement speeches from CS-01 to CS-20 contained positive politeness strategies, thus including a convergence accommodation style.

Through integrating these strategies, speakers effectively engage with their audience, balancing authority with relatability, and ensuring that their message resonates on both an intellectual and emotional level. Moreover, this delicate balance is essential in commencement speeches, where the speaker needs to inspire and motivate the audience while recognizing their achievements and aspirations.

Furthermore, the table highlights how these politeness strategies are employed in specific statements, illustrating the diverse ways in which they contribute to the speeches’ overall effectiveness and impact. Each serving to either enhance or mitigate the audience’s face needs.

Table 2. *Communication Accommodation Style Utilized in Commencement Speeches*

<i>Politeness Strategies</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>	<i>Purpose</i>	
Positive Politeness	“Hello, good morning!” - CS-04	The speaker uttered this statement in the beginning of his/her speech to maintain and keep a positive connection to the listeners. These greetings are used to enhance the positive face of the audience, creating a welcoming atmosphere at the start of the speech.	
	“That's how much I love you, guys” - CS-06	In this statement, the speaker used an identity marker which is “guy”. Utilizing this kind of term will make the interaction more relaxed which makes the audience to feel included. It is a casual term that regardless of gender, everyone is included in the conversation and enhance the audience’s positive face.	
	“It is truly an honor to be here with you” - CS-03	The speaker used this kind of statement to enhance the audience self-worth by expressing genuine interest and acknowledge their presence and importance. This recognition makes the audience valued and appreciated which boost their self-esteem.	
	“I feel your pain” - CS-05	The speaker acknowledges the audience’s pain to provide support and reassurance. This statement shows how the speaker relate and understand the audience’s emotions. In other words, the speaker makes use of sympathy or share the same feeling to the audience which enhance their positive face.	
	“May goodness and mercy follow you all the days of your lives” - CS-07	The use of well wishes is another incorporation of a positive politeness strategy in a discourse. With the use of this statement the speaker is sending a wish for success. This statement enhances the positive face of the hearer and avoids any threat to it.	
	Negative Politeness	“... and I know it can be really overwhelming figuring out who to be and when, who you are now and how to act in order to get where you wanna go” - CS-01	The statement recognizes how overwhelming finding oneself be. This statement is a negative politeness the imposition on the negative face of the hearer is reduced with the use of words that show sympathy. This statement threatens the hearer’s negative face.
		“I hate to break it to you but the real wisdom that comes with age is that you gain a greater appreciation for just how much you don't know” - CS-08	This is an example of a negative politeness strategy since the words “I hate to break it to you” is used to lessen the imposition of the speaker. This statement implies a threat on the listener’s negative face.
“It breaks my heart to have to tell you that you can be talented, you can be gifted, you can be on the dean's list, you can be a scholar of the first order, you can be an outstanding engineer, you're going to be a great teacher,		In this negative politeness statement, the author used the words “It breaks my heart” to express that he is not happy with the next statement that he will utter. This statement puts a threat to the hearer’s negative face but the speaker reduces its impact by his choice of words.	

	you can be a doctor, a lawyer, an engineer but I will tell you that if you're black or brown you will go places where you're going to have to navigate a presumption of dangerousness and guilt." - CS-12	
	"... and I don't care how hard Life After College gets and it's gonna get hard." - CS-14	This statement is an example of a negative politeness strategy since it states a negative impact on the hearer's face by stating that the audience will definitely face hardships.
	"Maybe you got an email or two about it" - CS-17	The use of the word "maybe" here is a cue for negative politeness since it emphasizes a doubt between having received one or two emails about something.
Bald on-record	"I am asking you today to use them on behalf of our democracy." - CS-05	This statement uses a bald on-record strategy that specifically states a request. This statement implies a specific action to do in the form of a request. This puts a threat on the hearer's face.
	"Decide what is yours to hold and let the rest go." - CS-01	This statement in CS-01 is a bald on-record strategy that promotes efficiency of a certain task. These statements are telling the hearer a certain action that would yield the best results, thus its efficiency. This statement puts a threat on the hearer's face.
	"Trust and believe that your Stanford family will show up for you in unexpected ways." - CS-04	This bald on-record strategy shows care towards the listener. The speaker is expressing care through the utterance of an action that must be done by the hearer. Despite showing care, this still imposes a threat to the face of the hearer.
	"... at every table you find yourself, get aligned and stay aligned." - CS-20	This statement depicts a bald-on record strategy since it is an utterance of direct instruction to get aligned and stay aligned.
	"I beseech you to remember the lessons of the office." - CS-09	This statement utilizes bald on-record strategy that implies urgency towards the hearer. These statements demand an urgent action from the audience to do a certain act. Thus, this puts a threat on the hearer's face.

Emerging Themes and Supporting Statements in Commencement Speeches

Furthermore, the commencement speeches were also studied to look into emerging themes that are relevant and contributory to the overall message of the speeches. Table 3 presents the emerging themes and the corresponding statements that support the themes.

The first emerging theme identified from the commencement speeches is the use of politeness strategies as a way of promoting inclusion among the audience. This is an example of a communication accommodation since they are using words that identify the group as a whole and brings the audience closer to the speaker since they can feel that the speaker recognizes them. The use of the words "Class of 2023", "Class of '21" "Duke", and "UP" are examples of this as stated below.

"We are all very proud of you, UP" (CS-10)

"Congratulations, Class of 2023" (CS-08)

"We can do this, Class of '21!" (CS-05)

"Good morning, Duke!" (CS-05)

The second emerging theme identified from the speeches is the incorporation of humor in the speeches. To further enhance the positive feeling of the audience the utterance of jokes that are non-offensive and are relatable to the hearer are used as an accommodation style by the speakers. In this way, the hearers will be entertained and a positive connection will be formed among the two parties.

The first example in CS-01 uses a line from a song of a famous singer-songwriter. It mimics the line with a similar tune that goes "So we'll keep dancing like we're 22." Thus, in the speaker's speech it was related to the event, telling the "Class of 22" to just keep dancing.

"So let's just keep dancing, like we're the Class of '22" (CS-01)

The second example is taken from a famous motion-picture comic series. This humor puts the audience in place of the superheroes who guard the galaxy in the film. Thus, the speaker tells the graduates to go on and "guard the galaxy" or to journey with whatever is in store for their future.

“Now, go guard the galaxy.” (CS-18)

The last example is a form of humor that mocks the students for having bought take-outs and eating food that equates to the food they can eat in their entire lifetime.

“You got through a year of quarantines, Zoom classes, masks, nasal swabs, and I’m guessing more take-out food than you thought you’d eat in a lifetime—and you’re graduating.” (CS-13)

Another identified theme from the speeches is the acknowledgement of the struggles and efforts of the students. Most of the speakers mentioned in their speeches their recognition of the hard work that the students endured throughout their journey. In the statement below, CS-01 recognized the students' works and struggles just to reach the place where they are today.

“You've worked and struggled and sacrificed and studied and dreamed your way here today” (CS-01)

Table 3. *The Emerging Themes of Commencement Speeches*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Promotion of Shared identity	“We are all very proud of you, UP” - CS-10 “Congratulations, class of 2023” - CS-08 “We can do this, Class of 21!” - CS-05 “Good morning, Duke!” - CS-05
Incorporation of Humor	“So, let's just keep dancing, like we're the Class of '22” - CS-01 “Now, go guard the galaxy.” - CS-18 “You got through a year of quarantines, Zoom classes, masks, nasal swabs, and I’m guessing more take-out food than you thought you’d eat in a lifetime—and you’re graduating.” - CS-13
Acknowledgement of Struggles and Efforts	“You've worked and struggled and sacrificed and studied and dreamed your way here today” - CS-01 “Yes, you've made it through a lot yet somehow you got here” - CS-02 “Your class is the toughest class to have ever graduated college in recent history” - CS-06
Sharing of Personal Experiences	“I’ve stumbled on three answers that I'll share with you today.” - CS-05 “I’m going to share mine” - CS-09 “... and so tonight, I thought I would share some advice, some lessons I learned along the way on how to make the most of that opportunity.” - CS-13 “But I do have some lessons I wanna share” - CS-16

Similarly, CS-02 affirmed that the students got to the point of their life during their graduation because of the different challenges and obstacles they went through in the past years of their education.

“Yes, you've made it through a lot yet somehow you got here” (CS-02)

Likewise, the use of the word “toughest” in CS-06 refers to how much strength, and effort the audience gave just to overcome the hardships of the pandemic and facing online classes even with the health threat that is going on around the world.

“Your class is the toughest class to have ever graduated college in recent history” (CS-06)

Finally, the fourth emerging theme detected from the speeches is the sharing of personal experiences by the speakers. The speakers incorporated stories that depicted their past experiences in college or even the lessons they have learned after they graduated. This sharing of experiences was a theme common to the speeches since it promoted a sense of connection with the audience by the speaker's initiative of letting them have a glimpse of what the speaker has experienced in the past. The statements CS-05, CS-09, CS-13 and CS-16 below present how these stories were shared in the speeches.

“I’ve stumbled on three answers that I'll share with you today.” (CS-05)

“I'm going to share mine” (CS-09)

“... and so tonight, I thought I would share some advice, some lessons I learned along the way on how to make the most of that opportunity.” (CS-13)

“But I do have some lessons I wanna share” (CS-16)

Politeness Strategies Utilized in the Commencement Speeches

The results of this discourse analysis revealed that the commencement speeches incorporated 3 out of 4 politeness strategies. Specifically, it included positive politeness, negative politeness, and bald on-record strategies. However, the use of an off-record

strategy was not detected. The results show positive politeness as the top politeness strategy commonly uttered by the commencement speakers, followed by bald on-record strategy, and the negative politeness strategy with the least utterance.

Positive Politeness Strategy

A study by Rejeki and Azizah's (2019) on EFL learners, following Brown and Levinson's theory, detected positive politeness strategy with the highest number of usages corresponding to 67 utterances in their speeches. In this specific analysis, the positive politeness strategy or the use of politeness cues that enhances the positive face of the hearer is the top politeness strategy used in commencement speeches. All analyzed speeches in this study had this specific strategy incorporated in them. As seen by the researcher, this strategy remains the most abundant because it has the ability to improve the speeches and make it optimistic, since the aim of a commencement speech is to be inspiring in the first place. Strategies such as the utterance of greetings, using in-group identity markers, showing appreciation, sympathizing with the audience, and promoting inclusion among the audience are some of the cues utilized in all the speeches. Additionally, the researcher also observed the sharing of personal experience from the speaker in all the analyzed speeches. This is another example of a positive politeness strategy because the examples given were all giving the message of a shared experience and an inspiring event which helps enhance the positive feeling of the audience.

In a study on teachers' politeness strategies by Elisdawati et al. (2018), the use of positive politeness was identified as the main politeness strategy used to motivate students in learning the English language. The promotion of this strategy was used in order to improve the student's image of themselves. An example stated in the study was the teacher's utilization of positive politeness strategy by using call names that did not impose any superiority such as the word "students" instead of "children". Also, the discourse presented dialogues between teachers and students using the words like "good morning, ma'am/students", "how are you?", "thank you", and the like. In the same manner, this discourse analysis on the politeness strategy used in commencement speeches has detected the same politeness strategies like the use of in-group identity markers, use of greetings, and appreciation. Thus, the results of this discourse analysis are in line with the findings of the previous research

Negative Politeness Strategy

In a study by Balik and Alinda (2022), the most common politeness strategy detected from their social gathering's ceremony speech was negative politeness strategy as this enhanced the hearer's authority by not imposing too much on what the speakers advised in their speeches. This negative politeness strategy is the use of politeness cues that reduces the threat to the hearer's negative face. Based on the observed commencement speeches, the use of this strategy was present to lighten the impact of the criticism used by the speakers to emphasize the hardships that have been experienced by the students throughout their educational journey. In this specific study, negative politeness was expressed through the utterance of statements that imply sympathy, a lesser imposition towards the hearer, and the use of hedging. Overall, these negative politeness strategies do not hinder the motivational thought of the speeches since they still offer a good message to the audience while pointing out the hindrances that might come their way.

On the same note, Rhaif and Mubarak's (2021) study on American commencement speakers identified negative politeness strategies in their speeches. One common style used by these speakers was hedging such as the use of the words "I think" which expresses a consideration to something that is not known by the audience. Another is the utterance that involves a tendency for the listeners to assess their own acts of omission. In relation to this study, hedging was also detected in the commencement speeches analyzed.

Bald On-record Strategy

The last politeness strategy analyzed from the commencement speeches is the bald on record strategy. In Yahsia's (2020) study on the politeness strategies used by school administrators, the bald on-record strategy was the most widely used strategy. It also concluded that this strategy saved them time and it anchored their difference when it came to the age gap among students. In this discourse analysis on commencement speeches, the bald on record strategy was the second most abundant in the number of utterances. This strategy is the use of direct implication, without any minimization of the threats that may be faced by the hearer's face. It also dictates the hearer of doing something or acting on something. Examples of these utterances include telling the graduates to take part in different community endeavors, to trust the institution that they graduated in, or to challenge them in finding the real purpose of their milestones. These bald on-record strategies give out a meaning that commencement speakers are trying to tell students what they can or what they need to do in order to succeed in their next steps in life. Thus, they are using this strategy to yield an action in return for their motivational message.

The same as the results of this analysis, a study by Helmi (2022) on class discourse between a teacher and her students also resulted in the detection of various bald-on record strategies. This utterance was shown in an example where a teacher asked the students to collect their works so as to give them the lesson of how organization is important in their schooling. She uttered "now, collect your paper," which is an explicit imposition to the students, therefore is an example of the bald on-record politeness strategy.

Communication Accommodation in the Commencement Speeches

To answer the second research question, an analysis on the communication accommodation styles was done. This analysis revealed the use of different politeness strategies, specifically positive politeness as a way of convergence accommodation. This means that these utterances were made to make the speakers' communication style more familiar and relatable to the audience. Similarly, a study on

international students' accommodation and politeness strategies for dealing with conflicts had the same structure, wherein those discourses that utilized positive politeness were also examples of convergence (Sari et al., 2019). Thus, the use of positive politeness strategies in the commencement speeches, which were seen in all ten, are also examples of convergence accommodation.

This convergence contributes to the overall message of the speeches since it enables the speaker to develop a connection with the audience. With these positive politeness cues present, the listeners are able to relate, especially to the real-life experiences that are shared to them by the speakers. Thus, this strategy contributes positively to the overall message, making it interesting and relatable for the audience.

Emerging Themes of the Commencement Speeches

In the article of Greenlee (2018), it was mentioned that President Obama used a statement that reflected a shared identity and value with his audience. Similar to this, Miller et al. (2017) also included in an article that one way of forming productive relationships with your audience is to share similar events and experiences that would let your audience relate to you. Upon analysis, emerging themes were also detected from the commencement speeches. The first of them was the use of words that implied a shared identity. The most common of this is the use of the name "Class of 2023" depending on the year of the graduation speech. This is used to address the graduates and to let them feel acknowledged. This is a significant emerging theme and is contributory to the effectiveness of the use of politeness strategies since it also enhances the positive face of the hearer. Similarly, the use of in-group identity markers was also a common utterance among all the commencement speeches.

In Salem et al. (2020), the study on Jordanian students revealed the application of humor in their speeches as something that made the hearers feel more included and it does not interfere with the exact message that is delivered by the speaker. Also, an application of humor was an emerging theme analyzed from the speeches. With the use of jokes and words that made the audience laugh, the speakers were already building a connection with them. This style of speech makes the audience comfortable and gives them entertainment which results in their interest to the speaker. In commencement speeches, this becomes an emerging theme as it entertains the students and convinces them to listen to what the speaker has to say.

Additionally, the acknowledgement of struggles and efforts was a theme detected from the speeches. All the speakers had an utterance relating to their acknowledgement of the struggles and challenges faced by the students during their college journey. It implies an appreciation so that the students' positive face will be enhanced by the appreciative words that the speakers uttered. According to Noack (2021), appreciation is important as this contributes by giving respect, uplifting one's morale, and providing motivation to others. They will be able to feel that all their sacrifices are not done for nothing, instead it is done for recognition.

Furthermore, the last emerging theme that was a trend in the commencement speeches was the sharing of personal experiences by the speakers. Chang and Tanangkingsing (2022) mentioned in their study that giving out personal stories and experiences was a common practice for commencement speakers. In this analysis, almost all the 20 speeches analyzed had a part wherein the speakers shared life events, lessons, and advice for the students. This remains an emerging theme among graduation speeches since it acts as an important lesson that they can partake in with the students who are on their way to a new journey.

Overall, these themes are what makes the commencement speeches effective. It gives the audience the eagerness to listen to the message because they are hearing positive words. This makes the speeches motivational and inspiring for them.

Conclusions

This study emphasizes the use of politeness strategies in commencement speeches; however, its implications and benefits do not strictly apply to commencement speakers alone. This study is also beneficial to other professions, especially the teaching profession, because this career largely relies on communication to deliver their lessons and messages to the students. Thus, teachers would benefit from this study by understanding the significance of using politeness strategies in communicating with their students.

Given the results of the study, educators will know the importance of utilizing politeness strategies, especially positive politeness, to establish connections with their students. In their everyday interactions, teachers will be able to form a good relationship with their students if they use optimistic words that enhance the students' feelings. It will also enable them to convince their students to open up and share whatever insights they have, since trust is already being built between them. These connections will also be a foundation for the student-teacher relationship, making it strong and valuable for both parties since they will be in touch for a long time, if not for a lifetime.

The use of these politeness strategies in the classroom will also catch the attention of the students and influence them to be interested in the lessons given by the teacher. If used correctly, these utterances will also lead to a mutual respect between the teacher and the student when it comes to academic interactions. For example, the proper use of in-group identity markers, specifically "ma'am" or "sir", will help establish the standing of the teacher inside the classroom. Aside from this, with the educator's enough understanding of politeness strategies, the proper use of such strategies may also be transferred to the students through education. Thus, this transfer of knowledge will enable students to use such strategies not just in their academic endeavors, but in their social communications as well.

The researcher's aim to analyze the politeness strategies utilized in commencement speeches and how these strategies contribute to the overall message of the speeches, were studied and answered in this paper. This research provides an analysis of the different utterances that implied politeness strategies in the graduation speeches of various speakers, following the theory of Brown and Levinson as the main lens for this study. This also explains how such strategies, specifically the positive politeness strategies, improved their messages by creating relationships with their audience. Thus, this study contributes to the body of knowledge in the field of linguistic research and can be beneficial as a guide for future research of similar structure.

This discourse analysis provides data that are useful in the future studies related to the analysis of different types of discourse. Specifically, this study focused on commencement speeches delivered by invited guests in different international and national universities. So, to widen the scope of research, future researchers could explore more on commencement speeches that are given by student speakers, rather than guest speakers. Moreover, researchers could also choose to analyze speeches given on the local setting since there are only limited sources for commencement speeches at that level as of the moment. With enough resources in the future, an in-depth analysis of local commencement speeches may be conducted and fulfilled.

Furthermore, the researcher recommends that this study on politeness strategy be conducted on other verbal and non-verbal sources, since most existing literature are discourse analyses of movies or dialogues from an excerpt. Only limited analysis on the discourse analysis of speeches given in front of an audience are available in both national and international setup. Thus, this type of analysis could be done on more speech may it be academic or non-academic.

Finally, it would also be an interesting study to conduct an analysis on the reactions of students on these commencement speeches. It may be in the form of their insights collected from individual interviews, wherein they can express how they perceived these speeches and how these gave impact to them. With this, the effectiveness of the commencement speaker's use of politeness strategies will be verified through the perceptions of graduates. Thus, an analysis of both speakers' and hearers' sides will be explored and understood.

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